

Mild Balanced Neutrosophic Graphs With Application

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Abstract. The framework of mild balanced neutrosophic graphs extends traditional uncertain graph models by incorporating nuanced membership functions that capture truth, indeterminacy, and falsity simultaneously. This multifaceted approach allows for more accurate representation and analysis of uncertain relationships in complex systems. The theoretical foundations laid out through rigorous theorems and propositions provide a robust base for modeling real-world scenarios where ambiguity and partial information are inherent. Moreover, the application to medicinal interactions in diabetic patients demonstrates the potential of these graphs in decision-making processes for optimizing drug combinations, thereby enhancing patient safety and therapeutic outcomes. This study bridges mathematical theory with practical healthcare challenges, highlighting the versatility and applicability of neutrosophic graph models in interdisciplinary research

Keywords: Mild balanced neutrosophic graphs, Balanced neutrosophic graphs, Mild Balanced Neutrosophic subgraphs.

1. Introduction

The concept of fuzziness in mathematical modeling was introduced by Lofti. A. Zadeh through his groundbreaking works on fuzzy sets [20] and fuzzy algorithms [21]. Shortly thereafter, fuzzy graphs became an active area of research, especially following Rosenfeld's work on fuzzy relationships in cognitive modeling [16]. Recognizing that fuzziness alone may not sufficiently capture partial ignorance or conflicting information, Atanassov introduced intuitionistic fuzzy sets [4], further formalized in his text book [5], where both membership and non-membership degrees are considered simultaneously.

Intuitionistic fuzzy graph theory was further analysed by Parvathi and Karunambigai [14], who proposed structured approaches for uncertainty networks. Later extensions such as balanced and regular intuitionistic fuzzy graphs [9, 11], as well as clustering algorithms for knowledge discovery [10], enriched the field with tools for structure-based analysis under uncertainty.

In parallel, neutrosophic logic which is proposed by Florentin Smarandache inspired a more generalized approach to modeling ambiguous information by incorporating three components: truth, indeterminacy, and falsity [18] membership functions. Kandasamy et al. [8] formalized neutrosophic graph theory, enabling higher expressiveness for complex decision and reasoning systems. Subsequent studies explored properties of balanced neutrosophic graphs [17]. Broumi et al. [6] investigated on the concepts of single-valued neutrosophic graphs and planar neutrosophic graphs [12].

Moreover, interval-based and bipolar extensions were developed to represent uncertain data arising from expert assessments or conflicting evidence. Bipolar fuzzy graphs, as detailed by Akram et al. [1–3], introduced a framework for modeling systems with both positive and negative tendencies. At the same time, interval-valued neutrosophic models [15, 19] have been effectively applied in domains like shortest path computation, where uncertainty ranges matter.

Other advancements include the incorporation of decision support indices such as W -density [22] and the RSM index [13] to predict links in social and knowledge networks. Classical contributions such as the Erdős–Rényi model of random graphs [7] still underpin much of this work, providing a probabilistic basis for analysing network properties.

Collectively, these developments mark a significant shift in graph modelling techniques from deterministic to imprecise, from binary to multi-valued logic which paves the way for robust applications in data sciences, artificial intelligence, social networks, and decision support systems. This paper builds upon this rich foundation by exploring new structural and algorithmic properties in generalized fuzzy and neutrosophic graphs, contributing to the theoretical development and practical utility of graph-based uncertainty modelling.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. A single valued neutrosophic graph (SVN-graph) with underlying set V is defined to be a pair $G : (A, B)$ where

1. The functions $T_A : V \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $I_A : V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $F_A : V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denote the degree of truth membership, degree of indeterminate membership and degree of false membership of the element $v_i \in V$, respectively and $0 \leq T_A(v_i) + I_A(v_i) + F_A(v_i) \leq 3$ for all $v_i \in V$.
2. The functions $T_B : E \subseteq V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $I_B : E \subseteq V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are defined by $T_B(v_i, v_j) \leq T_A(v_i) \wedge T_A(v_j)$, $I_B(v_i, v_j) \leq I_A(v_i) \vee I_A(v_j)$ and $F_B(v_i, v_j) \leq F_A(v_i) \vee F_A(v_j)$ for all $F(v_j)$ which denotes the degree of true, indeterminate and false membership functions of

the edge $(v_i, v_j) \in E$ respectively., where $0 \leq T_B(v_i, v_j) + I_B(v_i, v_j) + F_B(v_i, v_j) \leq 3$ for all $(v_i, v_j) \in E (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$. We say A , the single valued neutrosophic vertex set of V , B the single valued neutrosophic edge set of E .

Definition 2.2. A connected subgraph H of a neutrosophic graph $G : (V, E)$ is called intense subgraph if

- (i) $V(H) \subseteq V(G)$ and $E(H) \subseteq E(G)$
- (ii) $D_t(H) \leq D_t(G), D_i(H) \leq D_i(G)$ and $D_f(H) \leq D_f(G)$

Definition 2.3. A partial SVN-subgraph of SVN-graph $G = (A, B)$ is a SVN-graph $H = (V', E')$ such that $V' \subseteq V$, where $T'_A(v_i) \leq T_A(v_i), I'_A(v_i) \geq I_A(v_i), F'_A(v_i) \geq F_A(v_i)$ for all $v_i \in V$ and $E' \subseteq E$, where $T'_B(v_i, v_j) \leq T_B(v_i, v_j), I'_B(v_i, v_j) \geq I_B(v_i, v_j)$ and $F'_B(v_i, v_j) \geq F_B(v_i, v_j)$ for all $(v_i, v_j) \in E$.

Definition 2.4. Let $G : (A, B)$ be an SVNG. Then, G is said to be strong SVNG if $T_B(v_j v_k) = T_A(v_j) \wedge T_A(v_k)$,
 $I_B(v_j v_k) = I_A(v_j) \vee I_A(v_k)$ and
 $F_B(v_j v_k) = F_A(v_j) \vee F_A(v_k)$.

Definition 2.5. Let $G : (A, B)$ be an SVNG. Then, G is said to be complete SVNG if $T_B(v_j v_k) = T_A(v_j) \wedge T_A(v_k)$,
 $I_B(v_j v_k) = I_A(v_j) \vee I_A(v_k)$ and
 $F_B(v_j v_k) = F_A(v_j) \vee F_A(v_k)$.

Definition 2.6. A connected subgraph H of a neutrosophic graph $G : (V, E)$ is called Feeble subgraph if

- (i) $V(H) \subseteq V(G)$ and $E(H) \subseteq E(G)$ and
- (ii) $D_t(H) > D_t(G), D_i(H) > D_i(G)$ and $D_f(H) > D_f(G)$

Definition 2.7. A neutrosophic graph $G : (V, E)$ is called a mild balanced neutrosophic graph if all connected subgraphs of G are intense subgraphs.

Definition 2.8. Two intense neutrosophic connected subgraphs H_1 and H_2 of a neutrosophic graph $G : (V, E)$ are called equally balanced subgraphs if

- (i) $D_t(H) \leq D_t(G), D_i(H) \leq D_i(G)$ and $D_f(H) \leq D_f(G)$
- (ii) $D_t(H_1) \leq D_t(G), D_i(H_1) \leq D_i(G)$ and $D_f(H_2) \leq D_f(G)$
- (iii) $D_t(H_1) = D_t(H_2), D_i(H_1) = D_i(H_2)$ and $D_f(H_1) \leq D_f(H_2)$

Definition 2.9. If $D_t(H_j) = D_t(G), D_i(H_j) = D_i(G)$ and $D_f(H_j) = D_f(G)$ for all possible connected subgraphs H_j of G , then the graph $G : (V, E)$ is called a strictly balanced neutrosophic graph.

3. Mild balanced neutrosophic graphs

Theorem 3.1. *For a strong neutrosophic graph, $D(G) = (2, 2, 2)$ and it is strictly balanced.*

Proof. Since all the edges of the neutrosophic graph $G : (V, E)$ are strong $t_B(v_j v_k) = t_A(v_j) \wedge t_A(v_k)$,

$i_B(v_j v_k) = i_A(v_j) \vee i_A(v_k)$ and

$f_B(v_j v_k) = f_A(v_j) \vee f_A(v_k)$

By definition,

$$\begin{aligned} D_\mu(G) &= \frac{2 \sum t_B(v_j v_k)}{\sum t_A(v_j) \wedge t_A(v_k)} \\ &= \frac{2 \sum i_A(v_j) \wedge i_A(v_k)}{\sum i_A(v_j) \wedge i_A(v_k)} \\ &= \frac{2 \sum f_A(v_j) \wedge f_A(v_k)}{\sum f_A(v_j) \wedge f_A(v_k)} \\ &= 2 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $D(G) = (D_t(G), D_i(G), D_f(G)) = (2, 2, 2)$.

Also all the connected subgraphs of $G : (V, E)$ has strong edges and hence $D(H) = (2, 2, 2)$ for all subgraphs H of G . Hence $G : (V, E)$ is strictly balanced. \square

Corollary 3.2. *A neutrosophic graph with few strong edges can never be mild balanced.*

Proof. If a neutrosophic graph G has few strong edges (not all the edges), then for any connected neutrosophic subgraph H will have only strong edges, $D_t(H) = 2$, $D_i(H) = 2$ and $D_f(H) = 2$. Hence $D(H) = (2, 2, 2) > D(G)$. Hence it may not be a mild balanced neutrosophic graph.

\square

Remark 3.3. It can be noted that subgraphs with strong edges are always feeble subgraphs of a neutrosophic graph unless it should be strong.

Proposition 3.4. *Union of two equally balanced connected neutrosophic subgraphs, with one or more vertices in common is also equally balanced.*

Proof. Let H_1 and H_2 be two equally balanced connected neutrosophic subgraphs with at least one common vertex of a neutrosophic graph $G : (V, E)$.

By definition,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D(H_1) &= D(H_2) \leq D(G) \\
 D_t(H_1) &= \frac{2 \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V(H_1)} t_B(v_j v_k)}{\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E(H_1)} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k))} = \frac{2a}{b} \\
 D_t(H_2) &= \frac{2 \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V(H_2)} t_B(v_j v_k)}{\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E(H_2)} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k))} = \frac{2c}{d}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_t(H_1) &= D_t(H_2) = \frac{2a}{b} \\
 D_t(H_1 \cup H_2) &= \frac{2 \left[\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V(H_1)} t_B(v_j v_k) + \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V(H_2)} t_B(v_j v_k) \right]}{\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E(H_1)} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k)) + \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E(H_2)} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k))} \\
 &= \frac{2(a+c)}{b+d} = \frac{2(a+ka)}{b+kb} = \frac{2a(k+1)}{b(k+1)} \\
 \Rightarrow D_t(H_1 \cup H_2) &= \frac{2a}{b}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $D_t(H_1 \cup H_2) = D_t(H_1) = D_t(H_2)$.

Similarly we can show that, $D_i(H_1 \cup H_2) = D_i(H_1) = D_i(H_2)$ and $D_f(H_1 \cup H_2) = D_f(H_1) = D_f(H_2)$
 $\Rightarrow D(H_1 \cup H_2) = D(H_1) = D(H_2)$. \square

Corollary 3.5. *If all the possible connected subgraphs of a mild balanced neutrosophic graphs are equally balanced then the graph is strictly balanced.*

Proof. The proof of this corollary follows from dividing the graph into two connected subgraphs which are balanced equally.

From the proposition stated above it follows that the union of two equally balanced connected neutrosophic subgraphs is equally balanced, the graph itself will be made to a strictly balanced neutrosophic graph. \square

Proposition 3.6. *Two connected neutrosophic graphs G_1 and G_2 with atleast one common vertex are intense subgraphs of the neutrosophic graph $G_1 + G_2$.*

Proof. Let $G_1 : (V_1, E_1)$ and $G_2 : (V_2, E_2)$ be two connected neutrosophic graphs with atleast one common vertex.

Let

$$D_t(H_1) = \frac{2 \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V(H_1)} t_B(v_j v_k)}{\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E(H_1)} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k))} = \frac{2a}{b}$$

$$D_t(H_2) = \frac{2 \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V(H_2)} t_B(v_j v_k)}{\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E(H_2)} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k))} = \frac{2c}{d}$$

$$D_t(G_1 + G_2) = \frac{2 \left[\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V_1, V_2} t_B(v_j v_k) + \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in V^*} t_B(v_j v_k) \right]}{\sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E_1, E_2} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k)) + \sum_{\forall v_j v_k \in E^*} (t_A(v_j) \wedge t_B(v_k))}$$

where V^* and E^* are the set of vertices and strong edges between every pair of non-common vertices G_1 and G_2 . Therefore, $t_B(v_j v_k) = t_A(v_j) \wedge t_A(v_k)$ for all $v_j v_k \in E^*$.

Since we are adding a strong edge between all the pair of non-common vertices of G_1 and G_2 .

$$\sum t_B(v_j v_k) = \sum t_A(v_j) \wedge t_A(v_k) \quad \forall v_j v_k \in E^*$$

$$\therefore D_t(G_1 + G_2) = \frac{2(a + c + x)}{b + d + x} > \frac{2a}{b} > \frac{2c}{d}$$

$$D_t(G_1 + G_2) > D_t(G_1) \quad \text{and} \quad D(G_2) < D(G_1 + G_2).$$

Similarly, it can be shown that

$$D_i(G_1 + G_2) > D_i(G_1) \quad \text{and} \quad D(G_2) < D(G_1 + G_2) \quad \text{and}$$

$$D_f(G_1 + G_2) > D_f(G_1) \quad \text{and} \quad D(G_2) < D(G_1 + G_2).$$

Hence G_1 and G_2 are intense subgraphs of $G_1 + G_2$.

In particular, $D(G_1) = D(G_1 + G_2) = D(G_2)$ if all the graphs are strong neutrosophic graphs.

□

Proposition 3.7. *Two connected neutrosophic graphs G_1 and G_2 with atleast one common vertex are not intense subgraphs of their union. (without proof)*

4. Application of Mild balanced Neutrosophic graphs

Here, we apply the ideas of mild balanced neutrosophic graphs in prescribing drugs for suitable patients accordingly. Let us consider the scenario where there are 4 drugs which could be prescribed for a diabetic patient. This applications determines the efficiency of improving the mixture of drugs given to a patient with multiple illness.

A graphical representation of truth membership, indeterminate membership and false membership is calculated based on medical treatments and the medicines prescribed by the physician.

A pictorial representation formulated by these are then embedded into a neutrosophic graph.

The following drugs have been used by an diabetic patient with various illness such as thyroid, heart disease and blood pressure. We identify the combination of drugs which would be suitable for an adult to take it as lifetime even.

We take metformin, empagliflozin, lisinopril and levothyroxine which are drugs used for diabetes, cardiac disease, blood pressure and thyroid respectively. In this application we are finding a solution for the problem where these drugs are given with limited dose to a person depending on the combination which won't affect the patient's health. The following diagram shows the interaction diagram of those drugs used.

FIGURE 1. Interaction Diagram of 4 drugs for a Diabetic Patient

FIGURE 2. Balanced Neutrosophic Vague Graph of 4 Drugs

5. Conclusion

This study not only establishes a theoretical foundation but also emphasizes the practical significance of the mild balanced neutrosophic graph model in addressing complex uncertainties in diverse domains. The framework facilitates better handling of indeterminacy and inconsistency in network data, which is crucial for real-world decision-making processes. Looking ahead, the extension of this concept to incorporate adaptive parameters will enable the modeling of more dynamic and heterogeneous systems. Applications spanning healthcare, communication networks, social interactions, and logistics stand to benefit from these advancements. Such integration paves the way for innovative tools that can predict and manage uncertainty with enhanced precision, ultimately improving the efficacy of solutions in technology and science.

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